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USING INTERACTIVE TECHNOLOGIES AND TEACHING METHODS AT THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE LESSON

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ANNOTATION

This article is devoted to the effective use of interactive methods in foreign language lessons and the methods used to make the learning process interesting. Theoretical data analysis of methods developed by scientists in order to ensure coherence between teacher and requirements in the learning process was also performed. Assimilation of educational material means that in the process of mastering, the joint activity of students contributes to the individuality of each, the exchange of knowledge, ideas, methods of activity. In addition, it takes place in a situation of kindness and mutual assistance, which not only allows for the acquisition of new knowledge, but also advances cognitive activity itself, transferring it to the highest forms of cooperation and collaboration. Interactive learning is an organization of the learning process in which almost all students are involved in the learning process.

Key words: pair work, rotational triplets, carousel, small group work, aquarium, unfinished sentence, brainstorming, Brownian motion, decision tree, judgment on one's own behalf, civil hearings role-playing game, press take a position method, discussion.

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ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ И МЕТОДОВ ОБУЧЕНИЯ НА УРОКЕ РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Данная статья посвящена эффективному использованию интерактивных методов на уроках иностранного языка и методам, используемым для того, чтобы сделать процесс обучения интересным. Также был проведен теоретический анализ данных методов, разработанных учеными для обеспечения согласованности между учителем и требованиями в процессе

обучения. Совместная деятельность учащихся в процессе познания, освоения учебного материала означает, что каждый вносит свой особый индивидуальный вклад, идет обмен знаниями, идеями, способами деятельности. Причем происходит это в атмосфере доброжелательности и взаимной поддержки, что позволяет не только получать новое знание, но и развивает саму познавательную деятельность, переводит ее на более высокие формы кооперации и сотрудничества.

Ключевая слова: работа в парах, ротационные (сменные) тройки, карусель работа в малых группах, аквариум, незаконченное предложение, мозговой штурм, броуновское движение, дерево решений, суд от своего имени гражданские слушания ролевая игра, метод пресс займи позицию, дискуссия.

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RUS TILINI O'QITISHDA INTERFAOL TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA METODLARIDAN FOYDALANISH

ANNOTATSIYA

Mazkur maqola chet tili darslarida interfaol usullardan unumli foydalanish va dars jarayonini qiziqarli tarzda shakllantirishda qo'llaniladigan metodlar ga bag'ishlangan. O'quv jarayonida o'qituvchi va talablarning o'rtasidagi uzviylikni ta'minlash maqsadida olimlar tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan usullarning nazariy ma'lumotlar tahlili ham amalga oshirilgan. O'quv materialini o'rganish, o'zlashtirish jarayonida o'quvchilarning birgalikdagi faoliyati har bir kishi o'zining alohida individual hissasini qo'shishini, bilim, g'oyalar, faoliyat usullari almashinuvini anglatadi. Bundan tashqari, bu yaxshi kayfiyat va o'zaro qo'llab-quvvatlash muhitida sodir bo'ladi, bu nafaqat yangi bilimlarni olishga imkon beradi, balki kognitiv faoliyatni o'zida ham rivojlantiradi, uni hamkorlikning yuqori shakllariga o'tkazadi.

Kalit so'zlar: juft bo'lib ishlash, aylanma uchliklari, karusel, kichik guruhlarda ishlash, akvarium, tugallanmagan gap, aqliy hujum, Braun harakati, qaror daraxti, o'z nomidan hukm qilish, fuqarolik muhokamasi rol'i o'yini, press-pozitsiya usuli, munozara.

In pedagogical practice, the term "active methods and forms of learning" has long been used. It combines a group of pedagogical technologies that achieve a high level of activity in the educational activity of students. Recently, another term has become widespread - "interactive learning". The modern science of education has approached the moment when there was a need to create pedagogical technologies that provide the most important thing in the educational process - the development of the personality of each student, his activity. It is necessary to create such learning conditions so that the student strives to obtain new results of his work and subsequently successfully apply them in practical activities.

The method of teaching the Russian language is currently distinguished by its innovative nature. Among the popular innovative technologies for teaching a language are such areas of learning as problem-based, programmed, computer, concentrated, modular, developing, differentiated, active, interactive, gaming. The role of interactive technologies in the process of teaching the Russian language within the framework of the Federal State Educational Standard is indisputable.

Motivation. To create motivation, along with problematic questions and tasks, skits, reading dictionary entries, excerpts from newspaper articles, listening to statistical data, different definitions of one concept are used. When organizing this stage, it is necessary to remember that what encourages one student to take active actions, causes a violent reaction, leaves another indifferent or leads to an insignificant effect, so I try to change the method of motivation from lesson to lesson, to diversify them.

Statement of goals. The lessons of interactive learning are different from traditional ones. Planning related to students' knowledge comes first: naming the features of functional styles, naming changes in Russian graphics, spelling, identifying spelling factors. Then the tools related to the emerging co-group are put in place: to distinguish the spellings that are subject to each appearance of the Russian spelling, to determine the stylistic connection of the text, to present the results of their work to the public. In the third place are the so-called goals of values: to express their attitude to the need for a single set of norms of orthoepy, to express their opinion about literacy, to produce information about the practical significance of the acquired knowledge. This stage has a huge burden: first, all students will be able to work, each student will be able to see what the end result will be, what to strive for; Teaching students to manage lessons at this stage is one of the professional skills of a teacher.

Providing new information. Since all the concepts that are being studied are already familiar to students in one way or another, it is recommended to start this stage with a brainstorm: "What associations does the word writing evoke in you?", "What concepts are associated with the word spelling?" The presented core thoughts are written on the board in a column and numbered. This type of work helps to select what is already known to students, and what is really incomprehensible, unfamiliar. The same work can be done differently: a keyword is pre-written on the back of the board, for example, orthoepy, and around it are words: orthoepic dictionaries, pronunciation norms, write correctly, speak correctly, speech, speech errors. Students are then asked to select the concepts that they think are related to the keyword. This version of the work is effective when students do not have enough ideas about the concept being studied. The third option for organizing this work: students are invited to relax, tune in to the topic of reflection, take pens and write down the thoughts that come to mind, while being reminded that there is no need to strive for logic, consistency.

New information is provided mainly on Worksheets, where questions and tasks are written at the top, and information is placed below. Textbooks, dictionaries, monographic articles, the word of the teacher are also used to provide information.

Interactive exercises. Working in small groups can be used as an interactive exercise. Carrying out this stage poses the most challenges. In shift groups, these problems are solved by rotation: from the active group they are transferred to the passive, and from the passive to the active. Because the group composition should not exceed 5-6 people. In large groups, sometimes there is not enough time to speak for everyone, it is easier to "hide" behind others, which reduces the activity of students, extinguishes interest in the lesson. It is good if students with different levels of knowledge in this subject are grouped together in each group, which allows them to complement and enrich each other. In order not to waste time in class, it is necessary to plan in advance what groups the students will be divided into. To do this, you can hand out cards with the letters that make up the keyword and invite everyone who gets the same letters to join. Job placement should also be considered in advance. During the break, you can put the tables on 2 or 3 and place the chairs opposite each other. This arrangement does not interfere with listening, students can see each other's faces, which helps them communicate together. For the effectiveness of cooperation in the field of education, the nature of its organization, in particular, the external regulation of the activities of group members, is of great importance. In organizing the first lesson, I tell students that when preparing a lecture, they should listen to all members of the group, try to identify the problem together, ask for help from the teacher if necessary, and then choose a speaker. During group work, it is necessary to monitor how effectively the joint work is organized, to help individual students to communicate, to provide the necessary assistance in solving the problem. Different groups will need different time to prepare a presentation. If not all groups are prepared at the same time, additional time will be allotted for them. The following work options are used to state the problem: one person speaks (at the group's choice or discretion); all members of the group perform in turn. But in both cases, students need to keep in mind that they need to speak briefly and informatively.

New Product. The logical conclusion of work on new knowledge is the creation of a new product. Given the large amount of information learned in the lesson and the limited time, as a new

product, students are invited to draw their own conclusions, to express their point of view, perform a new, previously unfulfilled task.

Reflection. This stage involves summing up the results of the students' activities. Reflections are facilitated by questions: - What did you especially like? What have you learned? How will this knowledge be useful in the future? What conclusions can be drawn from today's lesson? These questions allow students to highlight the most important, new, what they learned in the lesson, to realize where, how and for what purposes this knowledge can be applied.

Evaluation. This question is the most difficult for teachers working on-line. Assessment should stimulate student work in subsequent lessons. For the first time, if everyone worked actively, with desire, I give all members of the group the highest score. In the future, assessment can be entrusted to the group leader. This method of organizing assessment has a professional orientation - it teaches students to evaluate the work of others. You can use this approach: each member of the group evaluates each, i.e. puts a mark on each comrade in the evaluation sheet. The teacher collects the sheets and displays the average score. Finally, you can use student self-assessment.

Homework. After conducting the lessons in an interactive mode, tasks are offered that require a creative rethinking of the studied material: write an essay - a miniature on the topic, express your point of view on the problem, conduct a stylistic experiment. Such a task is more in line with the nature of interactive learning.

Classes built in an interactive mode arouse a noticeable interest among students, primarily because they violate the usual and somewhat boring order of work in the lesson, allow everyone to be not in the role of a passive listener, but in the role of an active participant, organizer of the educational process.

There are a huge number of interactive learning technologies. Each teacher can independently come up with new forms of work with the class. It depends primarily on the level of preparation of the class, on whether it is a senior or middle link, on how trusting and friendly the relationship between the teacher and students is. Interactive forms can be present as separate elements at certain stages of the lesson or represent used throughout the lesson.

Interactive learning technologies.

1. Work in pairs.
2. Rotary (replaceable) triples.
3. Carousel.
4. Work in small groups.
5. Aquarium.
6. Brainstorm.
7. Brownian motion.

Using Interactive Methods of Teaching Russian in the 1st year students. Learning the Russian language at school involves, as you know, the implementation of 3 main tasks:

- 1) to give students knowledge of the Russian language and the ability to use them in practice,
- 2) to develop thinking, creative skills and abilities,
- 3) to educate a nationally conscious personality.

The effectiveness of didactic goals - the consciousness, strength and depth of students' knowledge of the Russian language is directly dependent on the active interest in the subject, the desire to know it, that is, on the level of students' motivation to study the subject.

Starting to teach Russian, the teacher asks himself the question: how to make the lesson not only informative, informative, but also to keep children interested in the subject, the desire to learn, make the lesson interesting, increase students' motivation to learn?

Looking for an answer to this question, we can conclude that it is possible to interest, motivate students to study the subject by avoiding monotony, stereotyped work, using such forms, teaching methods that arouse cognitive interest and stimulate students' independent thinking. As you know, all the activity of the child consists of separate sequential operations. First, the student perceives the information, and then thinks on the basis of it. At the same time, interest in this process is very important. Moreover, all these operations are interconnected. Therefore, the teacher should direct all

his creative efforts to create a system of active teaching methods that will be aimed at enhancing students' motivation for learning and their cognitive activity.

The teacher needs to implement these tasks using game tasks and separate interactive learning technologies in the Russian language lessons in the 1st year student, which allow creating a situation of success in the lesson, including game moments, accompanying the work with a friendly commentary, which is very important for students in the 1st year taking into account their age-related psychological characteristics. At such lessons, the key to success is the ability to create an atmosphere of knowledge, search, interest.

At the Russian language lessons in the 1st year in the higher education, it is necessary to use such interactive technologies that will be accessible and understandable to students. These are such technologies as “Microphone”, “Brainstorming”, work in pairs, “Teaching - I study”, “Take a position”, “Unfinished sentence”, etc.

For example, we use the interactive technology "Microphone" at the stage of motivation of educational activities. Students should imagine themselves working with a microphone (pen, pencil) and, passing it to each other, express their own opinion about what they expect from the lesson (what to learn, learn, what to remember), based on the topic. In the same way, you can spend the lesson outcome stage by asking students the question: has the goal of the lesson been achieved? Did they learn something new? Have you enriched your knowledge, vocabulary, etc.? Did you like the lesson? How?.

At the stage of formation of skills and abilities, we use the interactive technology "Take a position". For example, when studying the topic “Groups of adjectives by meaning”, each student pulls out a piece of paper with an adjective written on it. On the board - in different places - sheets with inscriptions: "qualitative", "relative", "possessive". Each student must go to the appropriate sheet, name their adjectives and justify their choice.

Using these technologies in the classroom, you can see a certain result: students not only acquire knowledge, but also understand, learn to apply, analyze, synthesize, evaluate it. That is, such work contributes to a very high level of student activity, this is the result of the fact that the main source of motivation for learning is the interest of the students themselves.

The use of such technologies allows the teacher to solve a number of problems: to offer his point of view from the standpoint of scientific knowledge, and not force him to incline to his opinion, to develop critical thinking of schoolchildren, to teach them to see errors or logical violations in the statements of other students, to be able to argue their thoughts, change them, if they are wrong, etc.

They also help to increase cognitive activity, motivate students to learn the language of game tasks that you should try to use in your lessons more often (if this is motivated by the type of lesson, its tasks), because they, in combination with other forms of work, contribute to deeper assimilation of knowledge, individualization of learning, determination of the level of formation of skills and abilities of students, develop memory, attention, ability to analyze, compare language phenomena. In addition, linguistic games activate linguistic games to a certain extent for schoolchildren of this age.

In addition, the use of game tasks contributes to the development of a thinking personality. Firstly, such tasks are mainly search tasks. They put the student in front of the need to independently find solutions, and therefore, to recognize, analyze linguistic facts, compare them and formulate conclusions. And this develops the creative abilities of the student, attention, initiative. Secondly, working with game tasks creates a positive motivation for learning, awakens the desire to know. Thirdly, by independently discovering certain linguistic phenomena, the student gets pleasure, confidence in his abilities, which leads to self-realization of the individual.

The achievement of the above tasks and goals of the lesson is facilitated by a whole range of linguistic games that can be used in the 1st year: crossword puzzle, quiz, auction, language competition, linguistic riddle, linguistic task, “Steps”, “Crossroads”, rebus, “You -editor”, "Surplus", "Catch the mistake", "I believe - I do not believe", "Sorting", "The smartest", "Language duel", "The last word is yours", "Who is faster", "Linguistic relay race" ”, “ You are a teacher ”; “ Word Pyramid ”and others.

Game tasks can be used at different stages of the lesson, because they provide an opportunity to activate the attention of students, and work out the acquired knowledge, and relieve stress and increase productivity. Here are some examples of the use of game tasks. [18, p.16].

Topic. Antonyms.

At the stage of updating the basic knowledge, we offer the students the game task "Guess the riddle":

Short tail and long legs.

Night and day - in dismay

I don't know peace and quiet

I'm afraid of everyone and run away. (Hare).

Students solve the riddle. The teacher underlines a pair of words with chalk of different colors (short - long, at night - during the day, anxiety - rest).

"Brainstorm"

Auction game.

It is carried out in the form of an auction or a relay race: for 3 - 4 minutes. students should name as many phraseological units as possible with the words: head, tongue, eyes, teeth, legs. "Hidden Word"

Choose an antonym for each word and read the "hidden" word. All antonyms must begin with the same letter.

1. Specific. 2. Peaceful. 3. Unfortunate. 4. Passive. 5. Cute.

Game "Spelling Relay Race".

The class is divided into teams (in rows). A word with arthrograms is written on the board (for example, director). Each team member must write a spelling word that began with the letter that the previous one ended with. The team that completes the task faster wins. (For example: director - Mitten-atelier ...).

Topic. Noun. Repetition.

"Superfluous".

Define the "extra" word, justify your choice. March, tower, cliff, shoulder, hope. Yeast, joy, glasses, leaves, scissors. Postman, wife, elder, servant, orphan.

To check the level of assimilation of theoretical knowledge, we use the game "You - to me, I - to you." Students should prepare questions on the theory of the topic under study for classmates in advance.

Also, students receive homework (to be completed at will) of a game nature: to make a crossword puzzle, a rebus, a linguistic task, "An extra word". As a rule, children perform such tasks with pleasure, applying both knowledge and creative abilities. So, for example, when studying the topic "The structure of the word. Word formation" we use a linguistic game for classmates "Guess the word":

A) Guess the word in which: the root from the word earth, suffixes from the words spring, bed, ending from the word shovel (dugout).

B) Guess the word: state song + part of the world (gymnasium).

B) Guess the word: crow word + game card (kartuz).

D) Guess the word in which: prefix from the word colorless, root from the word water, suffix from the word paired, ending from the word beautiful (anhydrous).

In addition, we use non-traditional lessons in grades 5-6: a language tournament, a brain ring, a competition lesson, a travel lesson, a quiz lesson, a research lesson, etc., which also attract students and increase the level of cognitive activity and motivation for learning. learning the native language.

As the conclusion we can say that the use of certain interactive technologies and game tasks in the Russian language lessons really increase the level of cognitive activity and motivation of students, interest them, which contributes to the desire to perform certain types of work, and, consequently, to assimilate educational material in cooperation, co-creation, through independent work. These technologies allow the teacher to differentiate, individualize the learning process, develop the analytical thinking of students, form their skills of self-assessment, self-control of their

educational activities, promote the development of creative thinking, a culture of communication, educate an active person who can see, set and solve non-standard problems.

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СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

5 ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

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